

Impact of the emotional experience on the e-fidelity of the Moroccan consumer

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Résumé

Le monde assiste à une évolution de la technologie numérique qui coïncide avec un changement dans le comportement d'achat des consommateurs qui rend le client plus indépendant et informé. Par conséquent, les entreprises doivent vendre différemment et acquérir un avantage concurrentiel. En suivant le comportement des consommateurs grâce à l'utilisation de certaines technologies numériques, il est possible de personnaliser les expériences des consommateurs et de leur procurer des sensations inoubliables plutôt qu'une simple rencontre avec un produit et/ou un service. Dans cet article, nous nous concentrerons principalement sur l'expérience émotionnelle que le client ressent lors de l'achat en ligne, avec l'intégration des dimensions ergonomiques du site marchand (accessibilité, agent virtuel et sécurité des paiements), ainsi qu'en montrant le rôle médiateur de la confiance émotionnelle sur la sécurité des paiements par rapport à l'expérience émotionnelle et enfin en testant l'impact de l'expérience émotionnelle sur l'e-fidélité (état d'approche ou d'excitation). Pour toutes ces raisons, une attention particulière sera portée au choix des variables à étudier, à l'élaboration des hypothèses et du modèle conceptuel qui seront étudiés dans le cadre de l'impact de l'expérience émotionnelle sur la fidélité électronique au site marchand.

Mots clés :

L'expérience émotionnelle, site marchand, e-fidélité, e-client, ergonomie, accessibilité, agent virtuel, sécurité de paiement, confiance émotionnelle.

Abstract

The world is witnessing an evolution of digital technology that coincides with a change in consumer buying behavior that makes the customer more independent and informed. As a result, companies need to sell differently and gain a competitive advantage. By tracking consumer behavior through the use of certain digital technologies to personalize consumer experiences and provide customers with unforgettable feelings rather than just an encounter with a product and/or service. In this paper, we will mainly focus on the emotional experience that the customer feels during the online purchase, with the integration of the ergonomic dimensions of the merchant site (accessibility, virtual agent and payment security), as well as showing the mediating role of emotional trust on payment security in relation to the emotional experience and finally testing the impact of the emotional experience on e-loyalty (approach or arousal state). For all these reasons, particular attention will be paid to the choice of the variables to be studied, to the development of the hypotheses and the conceptual model that will be studied in the context of the impact of the emotional experience on electronic loyalty to the merchant site.

Keywords :

Emotional experience, commercial website, e-loyalty, e-customer, ergonomics, accessibility, virtual agent, payment security, emotional trust.

Introduction

Consumption has evolved and the customer does not only ask to buy a product by a click, but to live unforgettable immersions before the purchase (Bonfanti & Yfantidou, 2021), and from there, online retailers must realize that users are absorbed by the ergonomics of a website, which will make the online customer live exceptional, unforgettable, and memorable moments during his encounter with the merchant site that is transformed through the experiences (Schmitt, 1999).

Several authors have explained that creating a buying experience for the consumer involves dramatizing and staging the consumer and the company's offerings (Carù & Cova, 2006). Through the creation of an ambient, decorative and theatrical environment. In the same context, the experience is created when the company stages its products and services in order to immerse the customer in an extraordinary environment and to make him participate in the creation of his experience so that he lives moments of pleasure and unique experiences (Arnilawati et al., 2020).

Indeed, the virtual environment of a merchant site has a positive effect on the reaction of online customers, both on an emotional and cognitive level (Dailey, 2004; Dash et al., 2013). The online shopping experience can influence the customer's current decision and future reactions (Hakiri & Zghal, 2010). Accessibility, reliability and speed of merchant sites (Diouf & Lemoine, 2019; Kiryukhina, 2016) that make the consumer want to browse or not. While consumer behavior is related to the degree of certainty towards a merchant site, which encourages the loyalty of online customers through an emotional and lasting relationship. For all these reasons, special attention will be paid to the selection of variables to be studied in the context of the emotional experience in a virtual shopping place.

Given the significant advances in the marketing experience in e-commerce, it is clear that the academic literature does not provide the keys to a better understanding of consumer behavior as a whole. Especially since marketers and merchants are facing a strong technological evolution that has an impact on the changing behavior of electronic customers.

This observation leads us to look at the emotional experience and its effect on e-fidelity in an environment of a merchant site. Several questions arise:

What are the environmental factors of a merchant site that most promote and impact the emotional experience of e-customers?

Who determines the emotional experience in the e-commerce environment and what are its main dimensions and components?

What are the consequences of the emotional experience in the e-commerce environment on the e-customer's loyalty?

The main objective of this article is to study the determinants of the electronic emotional experience and their impact on the loyalty of virtual customers. In this respect, our ambition is to try to bring answers to the following problematic: What is the impact of the emotional experience on the e-loyalty of Moroccan e-customers?

This article contains a literature review, followed by hypotheses to create a reference model for relevant research in the field of experiential e-commerce marketing. Along with this, there are various key factors that affect the emotional experiences of the e-customer, which will be beneficial for e-commerce companies to retain their e-customers and also to compete in the market.

1. CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE AND ONLINE SHOPPING

1.1. THE CONCEPT OF EXPERIENCE

Experience entered the field of marketing in 1982, with the famous article by Holbrook and Hirschman "The Experiential Aspects of Consumption: Consumer Funtasie, Fellings and Fun", with the change in consumer habits, over time, experience finds its way into marketing and the idea has been confirmed by (Carù & Cova, 2006). Experience has become a key factor in understanding consumer behavior. Today's customer is not only looking for a product, but also for an adventure in a comfortable environment, a sense of adventure, fun and entertainment (HAMIDI, 2017).

Experiential marketing focuses on the customer experience and puts more emphasis on imagination, excitement, sensory stimulation, pleasure, environment and information provided to customers (Tynan & McKechnie, 2009), according to (Pine et al., 1999), experience marketing can create emotions by entertaining customers, letting them escape from reality, educating them and giving them an aesthetic of the objects or places they can see. Experiences are events that produce stimuli and often result from direct observation or participation in real or virtual events. (HAMIDI, 2017), suggests companies place the customer at the center of their interests, including more relationships and personality to provide a unique, memorable and emotional experience.

In this regard, The experiential approach is based on the sensations, pleasure, emotions, excitement and sensory stimulation that the customer may experience when purchasing or confronting the brand (HAMIDI, 2017). Consumer experience is the subjective state (Schmitt, 1999), accompanied by a variety of symbolic meanings, hedonic responses, and aesthetic criteria (Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982). Consumers seek authentic experiences rather than programmed experiences (Pine & Gilmore, 2007). Individuals want to feel and experience perfection in their daily lives, which makes them happier. Confirme (Csikszentmihalyi & Patton, 1997), Csikszentmihalyi's research revealed that the optimal psychological state of individual can be internalized through intrinsic activity and its conscious state (called flow¹) making him deeply involved and satisfied with the experience (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). All studies have shown that customers need experience and that experience as a source of a deep sense of pleasure creates a positive memory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990).

¹ Flow: a state of concentration so focused that it is equivalent to absolute absorption in an activity (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990)

A successful experience affects consumer sentiment. (DUBET, 1994) defines experience as a method of experiencing, of being invaded by an appropriate emotional state during self-discovery, and also of cognitive activity, a means of constructing reality and especially of verifying and testing it. Experimentation is a major innovation in the business world. Today's consumers find themselves in an increasingly complex environment, and those who provide unforgettable experiences to their customers are constantly striving to create superior value and competitive advantage. Experiences have become part of the show, not only in entertainment and pleasure, but in business in general (Voss, 2004). As a result, companies are recognizing that emotional engagement is critical to sustaining growth and profitability. They are therefore faced with the reality of adding new value.(Pine et al., 1999) , in their book "The Experience Economy", explained that creating experience production is a value that allows the company to be competitive and have a differentiating position.

Furthermore, experience is a key concept in the theory of consumer culture (Arnould & Thompson, 2005). This requires understanding all the mechanisms that take place between the moment a company makes a commercial offer and the moment a customer decides to buy a product, whether in a physical or virtual space. There is no longer just a seller, a buyer and a product, but from now on it is necessary to rely on the environment, the subjective desires and the well-being of the consumers.

Figure N°1 : Key definitions of the different experience concepts

Authors	Definitions	Qualify the experiential intensity
Holbrook et Hirschman, (1982)	Experience as a subjective state of consciousness, accompanied by symbolic meanings, hedonistic responses and aesthetic criteria. The consumer experience is a personal and subjective experience, often charged with emotions.	Hedonic experience
Pine et Gilmore, (1999)	the experience associated with a product or service is becoming an increasingly important differentiating factor.	The economy of experience
Schmitt, (1999)	Experiential marketing tends to offer consumers immersions in extraordinary experiences rather than purchases of simple products or services	Extraordinary experience
Csikszentmihalyi 1990	Optimal experience, where we feel a sense of exhilaration, a deep sense of enjoyment that is long cherished, does not come through passive, receptive, relaxing times.	Optimal experience
(Carù & Cova, 2006)	a personal experience - often emotionally charged - based on the interaction with the stimuli that are the products or services made available by the consumer system.	consumer experience

1.2. THE EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE OF BUYING ONLINE

With the acceleration of digital development and the changing expectations of consumers, who demanded exceptional experiences, in virtual shopping malls. This made a group of marketing researchers curious to understand more about this new consumer behavior.

In this day and age, the internet has become an important and necessary tool in the field of marketing. The internet relies on the web which facilitates interaction between the consumer and companies, as well as with other consumers (Hoffman & Novak, 1996). The web helps to enter websites through navigation in a simple way and via machines like computers or smartphones. The development of the internet has only increased its use, the emergence of consumers in a digital experience, it has become the goal sought by the majority of online retail merchants (Carù & Cova, 2006).

The consumer's desire for a pleasurable experience when shopping online, experiences sensory input from a series of stimuli on the website, such as textual information, visual images, videos, or sounds (Rose et al., 2012).

Some authors have suggested that e-commerce websites have an architecture very similar to traditional stores (Lemoine, 2008). The environment of a point of sale has emotional and cognitive effects on consumer behavior (Dailey, 2004).

In addition, the website is a way for companies to encourage customers to buy online. But, among the problems they face, the development of digital commerce technology and the rapid change in consumer expectations. (Davis, 1989), explained through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, have an effect on the attitudes and buying behavior of web visitors, that is, the usability of a website, encourages and enhances the user experience. A useful and usable virtual site is one that is effective, efficient and satisfying, which makes the customer spend more time surfing the web pages and also improves his feelings of experience.

The concept of online shopping experience is defined by several authors, (Armilawati et al., 2020; Rose et al., 2012), have considered it as a psychological state that appear as subjective responses in websites. The online shopping experience is like a consumer interaction with a shopping site, which is a cognitive and emotional interaction (Rose et al., 2011).

Indeed, academic research suggests that the online shopping experience affects purchase intent through consumer engagement, which improves the customer's desire to make an online purchase (Ma et al., 2020).

Numerous studies prove that positive experiences during online shopping are motivating factors that boost customers' confidence and increase their intention to buy online (Eneizan et al., 2020).

In addition, the positive experience opens the individual to a new experience and a desire to try new ones. But, having a negative experience has a huge impact because an experience can stop one's desire for a new experience. However, previous studies have suggested that when the individual has a positive, rewarding, and fun experience can mitigate and defuse the effects of a negative experience (Fredrickson, 2004). A positive experience evokes feelings of emotional well-being, which leads to personal growth and a desire to improve by continuing to participate in experiences that promote that growth (Baloglu et al., 2019).

A study that conducted an emotional and behavioral intention experiment while shopping online, participants felt positive emotions and the tendency to approach a website was positively associated with positive emotions (Deng & Gu, 2021).

The web atmosphere is an important tool that brings the online experience closer to reality. Therefore, the online shopping environment must allow for flexibility and a degree of mass customization in order to personalize individual experiences in which the environment and the individual are inseparable but united in the same space. Indeed, the atmosphere of the site that takes into account the different types of situational contexts of the online shopping experience (Kawaf & Tagg, 2017).

The emotional states that occur during the Internet purchase is a bias that has an impact on the customer experience and this influences the behavior and attitude of the consumer. The SOR theory, was and still is the basic theory of empirical studies to verify the influence of the experience on the attitude of the consumer. This theory was developed by Mehrabian and Russell in 1974 to assess perception, experience, and psychological responses to the environment (Bakker et al., 2014).

The SOR theory, has been used in several fields and has met with great success, as many studies have shown that emotion has an impact on behavior. According to which atmospheric factors are likely to influence, first, the emotions of the individual and then his or her purchase intentions. This model is traditionally used to account for the effects of the atmosphere of a commercial site on the loyalty of e-customers. Furthermore, from this article we will try to answer the problem of the effect of the emotional experience on the behavior of the e-customer by proposing the hypotheses and the conceptual model, we refine the initial conceptual model

of the SOR in the framework of the merchant site and specifically introduce the "payment risk" as a risk factor.[^]

2. ASSUMPTIONS AND CONCEPTUAL MODEL

2.1. THE ASSUMPTIONS

This paper builds on previous research showing the influence of atmospheric factors, first on an individual's feelings and then on purchase intentions. We built on previous research models focused on the emotional experience of a website. This led to the development of a conceptual model used to test the link between atmosphere, emotional experience and e-fidelity. Therefore, we propose a model based on previous research:

- The S-O-R (Stimulus-Organism-Response) model developed by A. Mehrabian and J. Russell (1974)

The S-O-R model studies the field of environmental psychology. It consists of three elements; Stimulus elements (S) belonging to an environment can act on the internal evaluations (O) of the individual, which in turn create responses (R). Researchers have focused their studies on the emotional behavior of individuals, using specific tools to measure emotional states such as the Positive Emotional Negative Affect Scale (PANAS) (Watson et al., 1988) and the Arousal-Pleasure-Dominance (APD) (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974).

This theory has been successful over time due to its ability to fit any domain, although a number of researchers have identified these limitations as it focuses on the internal emotional states of the individual while neglecting the cognitive states. Here we cite a few studies that have relied on SOR theory, to understand where it has shown a specific pattern in the e-commerce sector.

- Model by Chen Peng and Yeong Gug Kim (2014)

The study relies on the fact that the model considers heuristic and utilitarian purchase values as intrinsic drivers and treats the web environment as an external influence in the motivation phase (Peng & Kim, 2014). The study also examines two additional factors, attitude toward online shopping and emotional regulation, as activators of the purchase intention response. The SOR theory of online shopping behavior empirically tests theoretical relationships that may influence online shopping behavior.

The study examined two parts, the effects of intrinsic stimuli, the pleasure value of shopping and the utility value of shopping, which significantly affect the functioning of the organism, including the attitude toward emotional shopping and online shopping, , except the effect of the utility value of shopping on emotional shopping ; Attitude toward online shopping affects

repurchase intention and plays an important role as a mediating variable between intrinsic motivation and repurchase intention. While the values of hedonism and utilitarianism directly affect online shoppers' attitudes and indirectly affect consumers' purchase intentions. In addition, attitude toward online shopping may mediate the relationship between intrinsic motivation effects and repurchase intention, as well as hedonic purchase value has a weaker influence on attitude than utilitarian purchase value, it is stronger on emotional purchase.

The limitations of the study are its generalizability because the sample used in this study was mainly young adults. Chinese online retailers do not care about the personal feelings of customers. Indeed, the results of this study cannot be generalized beyond the study population.

➤ Model by Su-Chang Chen, Kuo Cheng Chung, Ming Yueh Tsai 2019

This model shows that sellers can use the utility and hedonic value of mobile payment to drive satisfaction and encourage consumers to use mobile payment for consumption (Chen et al., 2019). Utility value, pleasure value, and seller behavior can influence satisfaction. Indeed, the electronic payment is one of the most important variables of the website environment that can affect the behavior of the online shopper, despite this, few studies address the relationship between online payment and emotional experience. Among the research that highlights this theme the model (Wu et al., 2017) that mobile payment is positively associated with perceived pleasure. Our goal is to achieve an in-depth understanding of the impact of online payment security on a customer's online emotional experience. Combining a moderated variable between online payment security and emotional experience in the literature, emotional trust in payment systems indicates that users feel comfortable and safe with electronic payment services (Gong et al., 2020; Komiak & Benbasat, 2004). The high level of emotional trust depends on emotion, belief, and emotional reactions to the payment platform (Komiak & Benbasat, 2004).

➤ Model by Liz C. Wang, Julie Baker, Judy A. Wagner, & Kirk Wakefield, (2007)

The model studies the persuasive effect of avatars on online sales channels. Because it affects consumers and their purchasing power. Social cues stimulate perceptions of sociability of websites (Wang et al., 2007), resulting in increased pleasure and excitement, both of which positively influence flow, hedonic and utilitarian value. The study found that Excitement generated by social cues leads to increased pleasure only for consumers participating in the product category. In addition, the effect of arousal on pleasure value is stronger for women, impulsivity does not lead to pleasure for older consumers, and utility value is lower for this group than for their younger counterparts. The results indicate that there is a competitive

advantage for online retailers who use social cues that offer consumers a greater perception of human connection and the formation of emotional bonds.

Limitations of this model are that first: the results cannot be generalized to all online consumer groups, such as teenagers, who are heavy internet users. Second, this model does not include other variables that explain e-loyalty such as emotional experience and website atmosphere components (design, ambiance, payment security). Model by EL AOUFI, S., DAOUI, D., ASRAOUI, I. et OUAD, F.

Consumer emotions, the emotional dimension generates a mental state, accompanied by physical and physiological processes, which can manifest in behavioral changes. The model confirms this association that customer experience has an impact on customer loyalty in the Moroccan banking sector (Aoufi et al., 2021).

➤ Model by Ghada Bateeb, 2019

The model showing the effect of accessibility factors (navigability, sensory and sociability) of a store on the experience (Bettaieb, 2019). This model is still important compared to the others, because of the variables used to make the e-shopper experience memorable, but the number of factors is limited compared to the components of the website environment. These variables represent a positive relationship with the e-customer experience. We could also add that this study was validated specifically for 3D stores, but remains validated for shopping sites.

The combination of these models and theories allowed us to propose an integrative model of the various causal links studied in the literature, by examining the reciprocal relations between emotional experience and e-fidelity, through the atmospheric variables of a merchant site (accessibility, virtual agent, and payment security) and its effect on emotional experience with the integration of emotional trust as a moderating variable between payment security and emotional experience. Then, we will test the relationship between emotional experience and e-fidelity and its consequences on e-customer behavior.

Figure N°2 : synthesis of some works based on the SOR theory

Authors	Theory	Variables
A. Mehrabian et J. Russell (1974)	studies the field of environmental psychology. It consists of three elements; Stimulus elements (S) belonging to an environment can act on the internal evaluations (O) of the individual, which in turn create responses (R).	Stimulus-Organism-Response
Chen Peng & Yeong Gug Kim (2014)	Study on online consumer behavior the influences of internal stimuli, the hedonic value of shopping and the utilitarian value of shopping, significantly affect the organism's process. Environmental stimuli, affect both attitude toward online shopping and emotional shopping. Attitude toward online shopping affects repurchase intention and plays an important role as a mediating variable between internal motivations and repurchase intention.	Hedonic value Utility value Attitudes towards online shopping Emotional attitude
Su-Chang Chen ,Kuo Cheng Chung , Ming Yueh Tsai (2019)	the impact of m-payment on the emotional experience. utility value, hedonic value, and sales behaviors of salespeople have a positive impact on customer satisfaction.	Valeur hidonique Valeur utilitaire Satisfaction m-paiement
Wu et al., (2017)	perceived risk, perceived benefit, and positive sentiment have relative effects on consumers' acceptance of payment through WeChat. Perceived risk has a relatively small negative effect on consumers' acceptance intention. Positive sentiment and perceived benefit strongly influence payment acceptance.	Perceived risk Positive sentiment Acceptance of payment
Wang & al., (2007)	Online social interactions provided the perception of a human connection that enhanced customers' online experiences. consumers' online experiences by adding social cues that enhance their flow, enjoyment and excitement. pleasure and excitement are positively associated with flow	Arousal Pleasur Flow Pleasure Socialness Perceptions Hedonic Value Utilitarian Value
Aoufi et al., (2021)	Effect of emotional experience on e-fidelity bankingshows a positive and significant correlationThe	Emotional experience e-fidelity
Ghada Bateeb, (2019)	Accessibility factor and its effect on the emotional experience (Validated hypothesis).	accessibility (navigability, sensory and sociability)

2.2. THE CONCEPTUAL MODE

source: Author's design

Conclusion

Companies are facing a digitized world and a highly competitive market, which forces them to use certain technologies to personalize experiences and offer customers the possibility of self-service, thus immersing themselves in an exceptional experience. However, safe, fast, secure and positive online shopping experiences generate satisfaction and trust, and the increased frequency of online shopping can be synonymous with customer engagement with the merchant site. Loyalty is a deep-seated emotion that drives customers to repeatedly purchase a set of products from the same website, despite the situational influences and marketing efforts that can provoke consumer behavior, frequent visits and trust in a product or service are often associated with loyalty. The e-loyalty factor that can be affected by the components of the virtual atmosphere and digital experiences that affected the emotions of the Internet user when visiting a merchant site (Boistel & Laroutis, 2019).

Therefore, this article will serve to clarify, and know the degree of impact of the emotional experience to retain the Moroccan e-customer, and that this emotional experience is a point that makes the merchant more competitive on the virtual market. Although there is a stake in the Moroccan e-tailer's ability to provide an accessible and easy-to-navigate e-commerce site with events that can offer the consumer an unforgettable emotional experience.

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